

Supplemental Table 1^{21,22}

Primers used for *MEN1*, *KCNJ5*, *CTNNB1*, *GNAS*, *ATPIA1*, *ATP2B3* and *CACNAID* Sanger sequencing

Gene	Exon	RefSeq mRNA		Primer sequence	Amplicon Length (bp)
<i>MEN1</i>	10	NM_130799.2	Forward	AGAAGGTGCGCATAGTGAGC	360
			Reverse	TCGAGTTGATCTTGGTGGCC	
<i>KCNJ5</i>	2-A	NM_000890.5	Forward	GCTTCATTTGGTGGCTCATT	313
			Reverse	GAGATGACTGCGTTGTTGGA	
	2-B	NM_000890.5	Forward	GATGGTGTCTTTTTAACTCAAAGC	927
			Reverse	CTCTTCCTGATGCAGCTGAG	
<i>CTNNB1</i>	3	NM_001904.3	Forward	GACAATGGCTACTCAAGGTT	1060
			Reverse	TTACAACCTGCATGTTTCAGC	
<i>GNAS</i>	8 - 9	NM_000516.5	Forward	CCCCTCCCCACCAGAGGACTCTGA	434
			Reverse	AGAGCGTGAGCAGCGACCCTGATC	
<i>ATPIA1</i>	4	NM_000701.7	Forward	GGCTCTCTAGCTTGGGACATT	497
			Reverse	CGAAGGAAGAATGGATGAGC	
	8	NM_000701.7	Forward	CAAAGAGCTGGCCCTTAAAA	545
			Reverse	CGTGATGTGGCTCTCAAGAA	
<i>ATP2B3</i>	8	NM_021949.3	Forward	CCTGGGCTGTTTATCCTGAA	490
			Reverse	ACCTCCTCCTCCCTTGAG	
<i>CACNAID</i>	6	NM_001128840.2	Forward	TCAGTCTATCTCACATCCAGGC	390
			Reverse	ACCATGAAAGTTGCTTTGGGG	
	8A	NM_001128840.2	Forward	GTGTGTTGGCTGCTGTTGTC	451
			Reverse	ATGAAGCCTGGTGAGGTTCC	
	8B	NM_000720.3	Forward	AAGCACTGAGAGGTTTGGCA	372
			Reverse	ACACGGAATCTCACAGACAGA	
	16	NM_001128840.2	Forward	TTACTACCAGCTTCCC GGGA	419
			Reverse	CGAGGGATGACAGCCAAGAG	
	23	NM_001128840.2	Forward	AGCTCAGCACCACATGGATC	361
	Reverse		GGTGGCTGAATTGGTTAGAAAGG		
27-A	NM_001128840.2	Forward	GGCCAATCTACAACCACC	201	
		Reverse	GACCAAGGGACAGAAGCC		
27-B	NM_001128840.2	Forward	AGTTCTGGAGAGGGAGGACC	384	
		Reverse	CCTTCTCTGGGTATGGGGGA		
33	NM_001128840.2	Forward	AAAGTAGTTGGGCAGGGCTG	366	
		Reverse	CTTCAGCAGAGGCATTTGGC		